

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

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RDA for FAIR Data, Software & Hardware

Celebrating A Decade of Data
RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop

Version: February 2023

ABOUT THE WORKSHOP

The community cross-fertilisation workshop, 'RDA for FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) Data, Software & Hardware', brought chairs and members of RDA Working Groups (WGs) and Interest Groups (IGs) together, with members of the wider research data community to share and discuss challenges, solutions and initiatives associated with managing and reusing FAIR research outputs. The key findings of the workshop summarised herein will be used to direct the future strategy of the RDA community. Read more about the [community cross-fertilisation workshop series](#) in commemoration of the [RDA's 10th Anniversary](#).

CHALLENGES TO BE ADDRESSED WITHIN THE THEME OF FAIR DATA, SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE

Coherent and global implementation of the FAIR data principles across different research outputs:

- Software and hardware each face unique challenges in regard to the FAIR elements, and should not be treated the same as data outputs.
- FAIR software, machine learning and hardware policy has evolved separately from that of data, leading to divergence in implementation.
- Defining the scope and application of the [FAIR data principles](#) across all research outputs including: i) software and machine learning algorithms that combine data, software and computational workflows, and ii) hardware that comprises a combination of (often modular) physical design, data and digital content (software, computational workflows, dependencies or assembly instructions).
- A lack of understanding of the different roles and responsibilities necessary for creating FAIR research outputs and/or [data curation](#) as it pertains to software (e.g., researchers, data support professionals, service providers).
- A misconception that FAIR is the goal rather than a means for achieving the goal of data reuse.
- Understanding how FAIR principles relate to the [CARE](#) and [TRUST](#) principles.
- Extending the FAIR principles to the arts, humanities and social sciences.
- The FAIR principles are not consistently implemented in all regions around the world.
- FAIR assessment tools are not easily usable within different disciplinary contexts.

Metadata and technical infrastructure:

- Understanding how discipline-specific metadata standards and schemas have evolved over time.
- Ensuring discipline-specific metadata standards and schemas are maintained and remain relevant to communities in the future.
- Not all repositories and data service providers have resources and/or capacity for curation of FAIR research outputs.
- Increasing need for scholarly infrastructure(s) to provide functionalities for the creation of FAIR software, machine learning and hardware.

PARTICIPATING GROUPS & WORKSHOP LEADS*

[Data Discovery Paradigms IG](#)
Nominated lead: [Mingfang Wu](#)

See [community group card](#)

[FAIR Data Maturity Model IG](#)
Nominated lead(s):
[Edit Herczog](#), [Shelley Stall](#)

See [community group card](#)

[FAIR Data Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
Nominated lead: [Maggie Hellström](#)

See [community group card](#)

[CURE-FAIR WG](#)
Nominated lead: [Limor Peer](#)

See [community group card](#)

[FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) IG](#)
Nominated lead: [Carlos Martinez-Ortiz](#)

See [community group card](#)

[Software Source Code IG](#)
Nominated lead: [Tom Honeyman](#)

See [community group card](#)

[FAIR Principles for Research Hardware IG](#)
Nominated lead: [Julien Colomb](#)

See [community group card](#)

[FAIR for Machine Learning \(FAIR4ML\) IG](#)
Nominated lead: [Fotis Psomopoulos](#)

See [community group card](#)

*Workshop leads collected challenges, solutions and initiatives in preparation for the workshop and explained them during the workshop on behalf of their group.

- Ensuring search engines find relevant research outputs for a specific search query.
- Understanding the difference between the terms, 'machine-readable', '-understandable', '-actionable' and '-computable'.

Incentivisation and adoption of the FAIR principles:

- Lack of understanding about how to effectively and easily implement the FAIR principles within disciplinary and community contexts.
- The FAIRness of a research object is no guarantee of the quality of that research.
- Current FAIR implementation processes are manual and lack automation.
- More emphasis needs to be placed on data management planning to improve adoption of FAIR research practice and creation of better quality, reproducible data and software.
- Lack of awareness and education for how to make research hardware FAIR.
- Lack of incentives to adopt FAIR research practice; the benefits of producing FAIR outputs are unclear and/or not well communicated.

SOLUTIONS TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES

Diversity of roles required to achieve FAIR:

- Long-term involvement of funders, publishers, researchers, project managers and data support professionals to: i) achieve coherent FAIR research practice, ii) bridge gaps between academia and support, and; iii) make FAIR applicable in different disciplinary contexts.
- Ensure all involved recognise that 'FAIRness' of research outputs can change over time.

Metadata and technical infrastructure:

- Create rich, machine-readable metadata, in different languages, that is discoverable/visible and retrievable via different sources.
- Develop interoperable web search/indexing tools and APIs to make external search easier and support research workflows.
- Ensure interoperability solutions for discoverability (language and metadata) are applicable to local constraints, to achieve global information exchange.

Incentivisation and adoption of FAIR principles:

- Encourage use of the terms 'research outputs' or 'research resources' to overcome the perception that FAIR only applies to data and not other outputs/resources such as software and hardware that support FAIRness.
- Communicate that the FAIR principles should be regarded as aspirational and a spectrum, rather than a binary 'checklist' of actions, and that data reproducibility and reuse are desired end-goals. FAIR practice is a means to achieve such goals.
- Integrate FAIR research practices and real-world use cases of FAIR implementation into secondary and tertiary education and training.
- Potential for FAIR to be reassessed or further evolved with more components.

- Develop data repositories and curation services that have capacity to maintain and sustain FAIR data and metadata long-term.
- Create resources to monitor ongoing FAIR projects/initiatives at the disciplinary level to help less advanced disciplines implement FAIR research practices.
- Identify FAIRness metrics for software and hardware research outputs. Consider: i) the level such metrics would be applied (e.g., repository, dataset, researcher); ii) how such metrics might be applied in different research contexts, and iii) how metrics incentivise adoption of FAIR.

RDA community:

- Involve more early career individuals in the RDA to stimulate discourse about FAIR data with the next generation of researchers, data supporters and service providers.
- Prioritise focus areas relating to FAIR topics for groups to collaborate, build consensus and exchange knowledge across disciplines.
- Improve coordination and information exchange across groups to identify synergies, avoid duplication and bridge gaps.
- Periodically reassess RDA recommendations and outputs on FAIR topics for usability/applicability.
- Work with [RDA's organisational assembly](#) to encourage and advance the dissemination and adoption of recommendations and outputs.
- Collaborate with external organisations that focus on FAIR practices and guidelines.
- Ensure information exchange is global with i) multilingual translations of recommendations and outputs, ii) webinars across multiple time zones and/or in different languages.

ACTIONS FOR THE RDA COMMUNITY

Regular meetings of the group that attended this workshop. Including a follow up by the conveners.

Continued engagement with the [Research Software Alliance \(ReSA\)](#) to support FAIR principles definition for research software.

Create resources to map and track FAIR-related initiatives: outputs, active organisations and communities. **Extend to the disciplinary level** to help less advanced disciplines implement FAIR.

Targeted outreach through:

- Community specific and cross-community efforts
- Widely disseminating and promoting outputs.
- Working with those less familiar with the RDA.
- Communicating the benefit of integrating good data practice into educational programs to secondary and tertiary education providers.

Identify FAIRness metrics for different research output types i.e [FAIR Data Maturity Model](#) equivalents e.g. the [FAIRplus Data Maturity model](#).

Multilingual delivery of documented research output and multi-timezone, non-English speaking events.

INITIATIVES & RESOURCES OF INTEREST

Community collaboration:

- Data producing / repository entities such as [Research Data Australia](#), [British Oceanographic Data Centre](#), [Pangea](#).
- Research communities: information science, information retrieval and machine learning e.g., [NII NTCIR data search track](#), [UNESCO open science](#), [African open data platform](#).
- Sustained engagement with the software and machine learning community [Research Software Engineers networks](#).
- The RDA-endorsed [FAIRsharing](#) registry works with the community via its Community Champions and the RDA. Example [output](#).

Projects & Organisations:

- CODATA [WorldFAIR](#) project ([outputs](#)) including a Cross Disciplinary Interoperability Framework
- Knowledge Exchange a study: [FAIR data and software supporting reproducible research](#). Investigating minimal requirements developing reproducible research practice.
- [The Carpentries](#): coding and data science skills.
- [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#), [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#), [ESIP](#), [FORCE11](#), [GO-FAIR](#)
- [RDA Tiger program](#)
- [DataCite \(PID Graph blog\)](#); [CrossRef](#)
- National initiatives e.g. [ARDC](#), [NFDI](#), [IISC national PID research strategy](#).
- [ELIXIR](#): FAIR software and standards for ML.
- [Zenodo](#).

Online resources:

- [RDA Plenary event recordings](#) and [10th Anniversary events](#).
- Mastodon servers for scholarly discourse. Articles on this: [here](#), [here](#), [here](#).
- [FAIRsharing API](#): machine-readable metadata for standards, databases and policies, which is used by many [FAIR assessment tools](#).
- [Paper](#) discussing the notion of research objects.
- CRediT Role Taxonomy [example](#).
- [FAIRplus Data Maturity Model](#).

WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

1. **Jean Abouardham**, Paris Observatory-PSL, LESIA/PADC, France, [0000-0002-0156-8162](#)
2. **Paula Andrea Martinez**, Australian Research Data Commons, Australia, [0000-0002-8990-1985](#)
3. **Rossella Aversa**, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Germany, [0000-0003-2534-0063](#)
4. **Louise Bezuidenhout**, DANS, The Netherlands, [0000-0003-4328-3963](#)
5. **Mareike Buss**, Copenhagen Business School, Denmark, [0000-0002-1459-1345](#)
6. **Giulia Caldoni**, Università di Bologna, Italy, [0000-0001-6105-721X](#)

7. **Xin Chen**, Computer Network Information Center, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China [0000-0002-7073-9201](#)
8. **Julien Colomb**, HU Berlin, Berlin, [0000-0002-3127-5520](#)
9. **Karine Delvert**, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, Lyon, France.
10. **Victoria Dominguez Del Angel**, Genopole, Institut Genomique Numerique, France, [0000-0002-5514-6651](#)
11. **Bernadette Fritzs**, Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany, [0000-0002-0690-7151](#)
12. **Małgorzata Galik**, Jagiellonian University / Library, data steward, Poland, [0000-0003-0361-8626](#)
13. **Francoise Genova**, Observatoire Astronomique de Strasbourg, RDA France, [0000-0002-6318-5028](#)
14. **Julian Lopez Gordillo**, Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands, [0000-0003-0401-5122](#)
15. **Kathleen Gregory**, University of Vienna, University of Ottawa, Canada, [0000-0001-5475-8632](#)
16. **Maggie Hellström**, ICOS Carbon Portal & Lund University, Sweden, [0000-0002-4154-2610](#)
17. **Tom Honeyman**, Australian Research Data Commons, Australia, [0000-0001-9448-4023](#)
18. **Malika Ihle**, LMU University of Munich Open Science Center coordinator, Germany, [0000-0002-3242-5981](#)
19. **Santosh Ilamparuthi**, TU Delft, Netherlands, [0000-0001-5101-7898](#)
20. **Nat Irwin**, OpenTEAM, USA
21. **Beth Knazook**, Digital Repository of Ireland, Ireland, [0000-0003-3108-3921](#)
22. **Stefanie Kethers**, Australian Research Data Commons, Australia, [0000-0002-1730-476X](#)
23. **Qian Li**, Tsinghua University, China, [0000-0003-3562-1627](#)
24. **Paulette Lieby**, France, Institut Français de Bioinformatique, ELIXIR-FR, France, [0000-0002-9289-9652](#)
25. **Allyson Lister**, University of Oxford, UK, [0000-0002-7702-4495](#)
26. **Carlos Martinez**, Netherlands eScience Center, The Netherlands, [0000-0001-5565-7577](#)
27. **Paula Martinez Lavanchy**, TU Delft Library, The Netherlands, [0000-0003-1448-0917](#)
28. **Hannah Mihai**, DeiC, Denmark, [0000-0002-0454-4289](#)
29. **Nadica Miljković**, University of Belgrade, Serbia and University of Ljubljana, Slovenia, [0000-0002-3933-6076](#)
30. **Adam Vials Moore**, Jisc, UK, [0000-0002-2085-1908](#)

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31. **Joan Murphy**, Digital Repository of Ireland, Ireland, [0000-0001-6428-5875](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6428-5875)
32. **Özlem Özkan**, Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC), Germany, [0000-0003-1965-7996](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1965-7996)
33. **Leonidas Pispiringas**, OpenAIRE, Greece, [0000-0002-7111-094X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7111-094X)
34. **Fotis Psomopoulos**, Institute of Applied Biosciences, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Greece, [0000-0002-0222-4273](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0222-4273)
35. **Laurents Sesink**, SURF, The Netherlands, [0000-0001-7880-5413](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7880-5413)
36. **Lara Skelly**, Loughborough University, UK, [0000-0002-2301-1242](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2301-1242)
37. **Alison Specht**, TERN and University of Queensland, Australia, [0000-0002-2623-0854](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2623-0854)
38. **Rainer Stotzka**, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Germany, rainer.stotzka@kit.edu
39. **Alexander Struck**, Cluster of Excellence Matters of Activity, Germany, [0000-0002-1173-9228](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1173-9228)
40. **Johan van Soest**, Maastricht University, The Netherlands, [0000-0003-2548-0330](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2548-0330)
41. **Mingfang Wu**, Australian Research Data Commons, Australia, [0000-0003-1206-3431](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1206-3431)
42. **Hu Xiaoyan**, National Space Science Center, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China, [0000-0002-6491-9118](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6491-9118)

For more information about the RDA community cross-fertilisation workshop series, please contact:

- Connie Clare, Community Development Manager (connie.clare@rda-foundation.org);
- Kathryn Barker, Community Development manager Australasia (kathryn.barker@ardc.edu.au)

To become a member of the RDA, register [here](#).